
REBUILD

Working Paper

Fiscal Capacity

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Abstract

This chapter examines the notion of fiscal capacity – as a centralized budget, funded by own resources, to be spent in pursuance of strategic priorities – in the European Union (EU). The chapter explains that the EU's Economic & Monetary Union (EMU) launched by the Treaty of Maastricht was asymmetry, as it lacked a fiscal capacity. The chapter analyses the EU responses to the euro-crisis and underlines that these did not lead to a fiscal capacity, but rather resulted in the set up of a financial assistance facility, the European Stability Mechanism (ESM), which lacks the feature of a fiscal capacity. Instead, the chapter examines the EU responses to Covid-19 and argues that through the Next Generation EU (NGEU) Recovery Fund the EU has now acquired a fiscal capacity. As the chapter points out, NGEU rebalances EMU and while its approval can be explained in view of the specific circumstances posed by the pandemic, it will likely leave a legacy in the EU constitutional architecture of economic governance.

Keywords

Fiscal Capacity, Economic & Monetary Union, Euro-Crisis, European Stability Mechanism, Covid-19 pandemic, Next Generation EU

1. Introduction

The establishment of Economic and Monetary Union (EMU) with the Treaty of Maastricht represented a milestone for the European Union (EU) and a major step forward for the project of European integration. Since 1992, the EU has been endowed with a framework to coordinate the member states economic policies, and since 2002, when the euro started circulating as a legal tender, the majority of EU member states has had a single currency. Nevertheless, EMU was established through a compromise, and as such its original set-up revealed an asymmetry between the economic and the monetary legs of integration. In particular, the EU originally lacked a centralized fiscal capacity, that is a centralized budget, funded by own resources, to undertake counter-cyclical policies in case of asymmetric economic shocks.

The EU responses to the euro-crisis led to a number of significant institutional innovations to support EMU, including the creation of a European Stability Mechanism (ESM), but did not

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fundamentally complete the EU architecture of economic governance with a fiscal capacity. The responses to the Covid-19 pandemic, on the contrary, marked a turning point in EMU, notably thanks to the establishment of the Next Generation EU (NGEU) Recovery Fund. NGEU is a special budget, worth 800bn€, funded through the issuance of common EU debt; it is disbursed to member states in the form of both loans and grants; and it will have to be repaid long-term through the introduction of new EU taxes. By endowing the EU with borrowing, spending and taxing powers, NGEU has endowed the EU with a fiscal capacity – going a long way towards completing the constitutional architecture of EMU.

This chapter is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the core legal features of EMU's original settlement and the developments brought about in response to the euro-crisis. Section 3 focuses on NGEU and highlights how the responses to the pandemic impacted on EMU. Section 4 concludes contrasting the ESM and NGEU and discussing some future prospects.

2. EMU and the euro-crisis

The establishment of EMU was a momentous event in the history of European integration. However, as a long body of historical research has pointed out, EMU was the result of a political compromise (James 2014). While in the run-up to the Maastricht Treaty many economists (Eichengreen 1993) had emphasized the importance of integrating in parallel both monetary and fiscal policies, the Treaty fully federalized monetary policy while leaving instead economic policy mostly decentralized, subject to a number of fiscal rules. These were condensed in the Stability and Growth Pact, attached as Protocol No. 12 to the TFEU, which required state to avoid annual budget deficits over 3% of gross domestic product (gdp), and to reduce public debt to 60% of gdp. Moreover, to increase the credibility of these fiscal rules, the Treaty also introduced a no bail-out clause, currently Article 125 TFEU, which prohibited EU institutions and member states from supporting other member states facing a fiscal crisis. This architecture was regarded as sufficient to ensure prudent public finances, and the Maastricht Treaty did not attribute to the EU institutions a real fiscal capacity to tackle downturns in the business cycle.

The original settlement of EMU, however, was profoundly tested by the outburst of the euro-crisis around 2009. In fact, the deficiencies of EMU transformed a financial crisis into an existential challenge for the EU, to the point that the survival of the euro as a currency union was itself at a point in question. Yet, through their concerted action, the EU institutions and the member states managed to address at least the most immediate effects of the euro-crisis by reforming the constitutional architecture of EMU. In particular, three main legal and institutional responses to the euro-crisis took place (Fabbrini 2016). First, EU institutions and member states strengthened budgetary constraints, acting on the assumption that the lax enforcement of the fiscal rules was the main cause of the euro-crisis. Second, the EU institutions and member states also created new governance mechanisms. In particular, in order to ensure a better surveillance of budget rules, a new European Semester was created, on the basis of which member states submit their draft budget bills to the European Commission for preliminary assessment, before these are approved by national parliaments.

Third and crucially, then, EU institutions and member states created new mechanisms of financial stabilization for countries in fiscal stress, moving beyond a strict construction of the no-bailout rule. In particular, in May 2010, the Council of the EU adopted, on the basis of

Article 122(2) TFEU, a regulation establishing a European Financial Stabilization Mechanism (EFSM) – a temporary scheme, with a budget of 60bn€, to grant immediate bilateral financial assistance to Greece.² Subsequently, through a private company incorporated under Luxembourg law, the Heads of State and Government of the Eurozone established a European Financial Stability Facility (EFSF).³ With a budget of up to 440bn€, the EFSF was charged to operate beyond the short-term emergency which had prompted the creation of the EFSM, and it provided support to Ireland, Portugal, and (for a second time) Greece.

Finally, with the aim to set up a long-term mechanism to stabilize the Eurozone, and on the assumption that a brand new legal basis was needed in the Treaty to avoid incompatibilities with Article 125 TFEU, the EU member states unanimously secured through a simplified revision procedure an amendment to Article 136 TFEU: This allowed the establishment of a permanent stability mechanism for the EMU.⁴ On this basis, the Eurozone countries set up the ESM through an international treaty.⁵ A first version of the treaty establishing the ESM was concluded in 2011. It was then revised and signed again by the member states of the Eurozone in February 2012, and it entered into force in November 2012. Since its entry into force, the ESM took over the operations of the EFSF and EFSM, and provided financial support to Greece (for a third time), as well as to Cyprus and Spain (only to its banking sector).

The ESM is an international institution, modelled on the International Monetary Fund (IMF), whose purpose is “to mobilise funding and provide stability support under strict conditionality, appropriate to the financial assistance instrument chosen, to the benefit of ESM Members which are experiencing, or are threatened by, severe financing problems, if indispensable to safeguard the financial stability of the euro area as a whole and of its Member States.”⁶ Eurozone member states contribute to the authorized capital stock of the ESM—totaling 700bn€⁷—pro-quota on the basis of the subscription by their national central banks to the capital of the European Central Bank (ECB).⁸

The ESM can grant financial support to a state in need,⁹ provide precautionary financial assistance,¹⁰ directly recapitalize banks,¹¹ grant loans,¹² and purchase government bonds on the primary and secondary market.¹³ ESM decisions are mainly taken by the Board of Governors—consisting of the Ministries of Finance of the Eurozone member states—on the basis of unanimity rule.¹⁴ Nevertheless, “an emergency voting procedure shall be used where the Commission and the ECB both conclude that a failure to urgently adopt a decision to

² See Council Regulation No. 407/2010/EU of 11 May 2010 establishing a European financial stabilisation mechanism OJ 2010 L 118/1.

³ See Decisions of the Representatives of the Government of the Euro Area Member States Meeting within the Council of the EU, ECOFIN, 9 May 2010. Doc. No. 9614/10.

⁴ See European Council Decision No. 2011/199/EU of 25 March 2011, amending Article 136 TFEU with regard to a stability mechanism for Member States whose currency is the euro OJ 2011 L 91/1.

⁵ See Treaty Establishing the European Stability Mechanism [hereinafter ESM Treaty], 25 March 2011, available at <http://www.european-council.europa.eu/media/582311/05-tesm2.en12.pdf> (last visited 1 June 2014).

⁶ Art 3 ESM Treaty.

⁷ Art 8 ESM Treaty.

⁸ Art 11 and Annex 1 ESM Treaty.

⁹ Art 13 ESM Treaty.

¹⁰ Art 14 ESM Treaty.

¹¹ Art 15 ESM Treaty.

¹² Art 16 ESM Treaty.

¹³ Arts 17 and 18 ESM Treaty.

¹⁴ Art 4 ESM Treaty.

grant or implement financial assistance [...] would threaten the economic and financial sustainability of the euro area.”¹⁵ In this case, a decision requires only a qualified majority of 85% of the votes cast, calculated on the basis of the contributing shares to the ESM capital, with the practical consequences that 2 member states—Germany and France—can alone veto any decision. Any dispute involving the ESM Treaty can be subject to adjudication before the ECJ,¹⁶ which eventually confirmed also the legality of the ESM.¹⁷

The ESM contributed to support countries facing fiscal crisis, and as such was hailed by some as an example of European solidarity. However, it is questionable whether the ESM solved the euro-crisis, and certainly it did not help to complete EMU. By all accounts, the key actor in resolving the euro-crisis was the ECB, thanks to its commitment to do “what ever it takes to save the euro” (Draghi 2012). Moreover, given its nature as a financial instrument to transfer funding from creditor to debtor member states, the ESM introduced harsh conditionality as a trade-off for financial support, causing popular resentment both in lenders and borrowers (Dyson 2014). As an international structure outside the EU legal order, finally, the ESM did not address the original gap in the EMU design – namely the lack of an EU fiscal capacity.

3. The Covid-19 pandemic and NGEU

The outburst of the Covid-19 pandemic in early 2020 had dramatic health consequences, but also devastating effects on the EU economy, which was still reeling from the euro-crisis. However, the EU institutions and member states took unprecedented steps to tackle Covid-19, drawing also policy-lessons from the mistakes they had made in responding to the euro-crisis (Buti 2022). In particular, in Spring 2020 the European Commission decided for the first time ever to suspend the application of the EU fiscal rules,¹⁸ the ECB rolled out a new Pandemic Emergency Purchase Programme (PEPP),¹⁹ and the Eurogroup approved a package of measures which included also an innovative European instrument for temporary support to mitigate unemployment risks in an emergency (SURE).²⁰

Most importantly though, the EU institutions approved the establishment of the NGEU Recovery Fund – an innovative budget designed to support the EU post-pandemic economic recovery worth 750bn€ at 2018 prices, which correspond to circa 806,9€bn at current prices. The idea for pandemic recovery plan was initially sponsored by the European Parliament (EP),²¹ and by France and Germany jointly.²² NGEU was formally proposed by the Commission in May 2020,²³ and endorsed by the European Council in July 2020,²⁴ after the longest summit since the Treaty of Nice. On that occasion, member states overcame the

¹⁵ Art 4(4) ESM Treaty

¹⁶ Art 37 ESM Treaty.

¹⁷ Case C-370/12 *Pringle v. Ireland*, judgment of 27 November 2012.

¹⁸ European Commission press release ‘Coronavirus: Commission proposes to activate fiscal framework's general escape clause to respond to pandemic’, 20 March 2020, IP/20/499.

¹⁹ Decision (EU) 2020/440 of the European Central Bank of 24 March 2020 on a temporary pandemic emergency purchase programme (ECB/2020/17), OJ 2020 L 91/1.

²⁰ Council of the EU Report on the comprehensive economic policy responses to the Covid-19 pandemic, 9 April 2020.

²¹ European Parliament Resolution of 15 May 2020 on the new multiannual financial framework, own resources and the recovery plan, P9_TA(2020)0124.

²² French-German Initiative for a European Recovery from the Coronavirus Crisis, 18 May 2020.

²³ European Commission Communication on ‘Europe’s Moment: Repair and Prepare for the Next Generation’, 27 May 2020, COM(2020)456 final.

²⁴ European Council Conclusions, 17-18-19-20-21 July 2020, EUCO 10/20.

reluctance of frugal countries to authorize the EU to issue common debt. In the Fall of 2020, however, further opposition against NGEU was raised by Hungary and Poland, which tried to use their veto on NGEU to prevent the entry into force of a rule of law conditionality regulation affecting them. Eventually, in December 2020 the European Council managed to overcome the opposition by Hungary and Poland,²⁵ and NGEU entered into force in 2021.

NGEU is established through a complex legal constellation (Fabbrini 2022). On the one hand, there is the EU Recovery Instrument (EURI),²⁶ adopted through a Council regulation based on Article 122 TFEU, which sets the overall financial envelope of NGEU and the general allocation of resources between its various programs. The EURI is then completed by the Recovery & Resilience Facility (RRF), which regulates the objectives and the governance of the main component of NGEU – the 672.5bn€ allocated to directly support member states. The RRF is adopted in the form of an EP and Council regulation, based on Article 175 TFEU, on economic, social and territorial cohesion. On the other hand, NGEU depends on the Own Resources Decision (ORD)²⁷ – the legal act of the Council, adopted on the basis of Article 311 TFEU, which established the revenues of the EU budget, increasing the spending ceilings and authorizing the Commission to issue debt. At the same time, NGEU is connected to the multiannual financial framework (MFF) 2021-2027²⁸ – the general EU budget, which is approved by the Council, with the consent of the EP, according to Article 312 TFEU – and, just like the latter, is subject to the regulation on the general regime of conditionality for the protection of the EU budget²⁹ – jointly adopted by the EP and the Council on the basis of Article 322 TFEU on financial matters – which is designed to fight rule of law backsliding and misappropriation of EU funds. The last piece of the NGEU puzzle is an interinstitutional agreement (IIA)³⁰ between the Council, Commission and EP, concluded on the basis of Article 295 TFEU, which sets out among others a roadmap for the introduction of new European taxes to repay the capital and interests of NGEU.

Besides its technicality, however, NGEU engineers a major policy shift in the EU constitutional architecture of economic governance (De Witte 2021) contributing to strengthen the fiscal role of the EU (Crowe 2021). In fact, by allowing the EU to run a large budget, funded by resources raised on the capital markets through common debt, and to be paid long-term by raising new EU taxes, NGEU constitutes a paradigm change for the EU, effectively endowing it with a fiscal capacity (Fabbrini 2022). This substantially helps to complete EMU, and to make the EU acquire features which are typical of federal fiscal systems.

NGEU establishes an innovative system of economic governance in the EU, premised on the idea that it is the EU's task to lead the economic recovery through new budgetary means,

²⁵ European Council Conclusions, 10-11 December 2020, EUCO 22/20.

²⁶ Council Regulation (EU) 2020/2094, of 14 December 2020, establishing a European Union Recovery Instrument to support the recovery in the aftermath of the COVID-19 crisis, OJ 2020, L 433 I/23.

²⁷ Council Decision (EU, Euratom) 2020/2053, of 14 December 2020, on the system of own resources of the European Union and repealing Decision 2014/335/EU, Euratom, OJ 2020 L 424/1.

²⁸ Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2093 of 17 December 2020 laying down the multiannual financial framework for the years 2021 to 2027, OJ 2020, L 433 I/11.

²⁹ Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2092 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on a general regime of conditionality for the protection of the Union budget, OJ 2020 L I 433/1.

³⁰ Interinstitutional Agreement of 16 December 2020 between the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission on budgetary discipline, on cooperation in budgetary matters and on sound financial management, as well as on new own resources, including a roadmap towards the introduction of new own resources, OJ 2020 L 433 I/28.

which financially support the member states. In the architecture of NGEU, the EU defines the strategic objectives, in line with political priorities it had championed for many years, including environmental and digital transition, and asks the member states to achieve these by designing and implementing NRRPs. Moreover, the EU makes available to the member states new financial resources, both as loans and as grants, to help them rebuild short-term their economies after Covid-19 and secure long-term social resilience. Crucially, with NGEU the EU finances itself on the financial market through the issuance of common debt, and therefore acquires autonomous resources: this overcomes the key problem of the EU budget and the ESM, which are funded by state transfers, breaks their politically and economically unsustainable logic. The 750bn€ of NGEU are not money of one member state which are transferred to another member state: rather, they are common debt which the EU incurs to support the recovery and the resilience of *all* its member states.

This has important institutional consequences for the EU architecture of economic governance. Needless to say, the EU system of governance is increasingly subject to an intergovernmental drift (S. Fabbrini 2015) – as visible in the ever-more-important role of the European Council, which in fact played a key role in approving NGEU. Yet, NGEU strengthens the role of the European Commission in steering the European economic policy. NGEU in fact, shifts to the EU a significant degree of new, *real* fiscal powers. In particular, NGEU vests the Commission with a power it previously lacked, namely issuing common debt on behalf, and in the name of the EU. At the same time, NGEU also empowers the Commission to support the member states with grants and loans, subject to the respect of precise milestone and targets which condition the continuing disbursement of EU funds. Although this power is subject to the approval and control of the Council, this constitutes a step forward compared to the simple coordination of national economic policies undertaken by the Eurogroup. In fact, the connection between NGEU and the MFF contributed to solidify the role of the Commission as a bulk EU Treasury:³¹ and the Commission has now even created within its internal organization an administrative unit in charge of debt issuance and management.

This has implications both in terms of horizontal and vertical balance of power. On the one hand, this influences horizontally the balance between fiscal and monetary institutions. By strengthening the Commission, NGEU creates a fiscal interlocutor for the ECB. In fact, the ECB had repeatedly lamented the lack of a single fiscal body at EU level with which to interplay, and NGEU improves this situation. On the other hand, vertically, NGEU increases the leverage of the EU institutions, and notably the Commission, vis-à-vis the member states' governments, because through a system of significant financial incentives they can influence national economic policies, favoring virtuous behaviors such as reforms and investments. The problematic institutional aspect of the post-pandemic architecture of economic governance is however the negligible role of the EP, which is cut off from the mobilization of EU resources and their control. From a constitutional viewpoint, this state of affairs is unsustainable and will have to be addressed, as will be pointed out also in the concluding section.

From the economic viewpoint, finally, through NGEU, the EU acquires the ability to stabilize the macro-economic cycle, intervening with own resources there where it is more necessary to ensure stable growth, high level of unemployment and economic convergence between member states. At the same time, NGEU allows the EU to pursue a number of European public goods – such as the protection of the environment, digitalization or social inclusion – even though this is done practically through member states' actions, funded by EU money. In

³¹ European Commission Communication on 'A European Minister of Economy and Finance', 6 December 2017, COM(2017)823 final.

fact, the largest share of NGEU funds, the RFF, will be spent directly by member states, not by the EU institutions. Nevertheless, by empowering the Commission to issue debt on behalf of the EU, NGEU de facto leads to the creation of eurobonds, i.e. supranational debt instruments, which can constitute a liquid safe asset, easily tradable on the international financial markets. This contributes to strengthen EMU, including the international role of the euro.³²

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the strategy embraced by the EU and its member states to address the Covid-19 pandemic crisis has been strikingly different from that followed to respond to the euro-crisis – and had different consequences for EMU. As mentioned in section 2, the EU institutions and the member states responded to the euro-crisis by tightening fiscal rules, instituting novel governance arrangements and establishing new mechanisms of financial support. In particular, the centre-piece of the response to the euro-crisis was the ESM. This was setup in 2012 through an intergovernmental treaty concluded by the Eurozone member states only, outside the EU legal order. The ESM was based on budget transfers and financial guarantees from the member states – with each Eurozone country contributing *pro quota* on the basis of its economic power, and enjoying a corresponding unequal decision-making power. As a result of this arrangement, the largest member states, and especially Germany, were legally vested with a right to veto any disbursement decision. The ESM, finally, provided loans (but not grants) to countries facing financial difficulties – and did so subject to harsh conditionality, enshrined in a macro-economic adjustment program which de facto imposed austerity.³³

On the contrary, NGEU is established within the EU legal order, and to the benefit of all EU member states. It is based on resources which are raised on the financial markets through the issuance of EU common debt, and which are transferred to the member states both as loans and grants. In NGEU no member states has more decision-making powers than the others, regardless of its size or economic might. Finally, in NGEU conditionality is not imposed as a penalty for having breached EU fiscal rules, but rather is deployed as an incentive to promote national reforms and investments, which will favor growth in the future. Figuratively speaking, one could say that while a stick was used to address the euro-crisis, a carrot was used to deal with the pandemic crisis.

How can we explain the difference in the responses to the euro-crisis and the pandemic? First, the euro-crisis had asymmetrical effects, hitting primarily the Southern European member states. On the contrary, the pandemic hit indiscriminately all EU member states – even though the health measures adopted by countries were not identical, and the socio-economic costs of Covid-19 varied from one country to the other. Second, the euro-crisis was blamed on the irresponsible behaviour of several EU member states. On the contrary, no member state could be blamed of causing the pandemic, which was an exogenous shock. Moreover, the moral issue raised by a global pandemic with biblical tolls prompted Northern member states to agree on greater EU solidarity via NGEU.

³² See European Commission Communication, ‘Towards a stronger international role of the euro’, 5 December 2018, COM(2018) 796/4.

³³ See also European Parliament resolution of 13 March 2014 on the enquiry on the role and operations of the Troika with regard to euro area programme countries, P7_TA(2014)0239.

Yet, while the EU's response to the pandemic profoundly differed from its response to the euro-crisis, and drew policy lessons from it, the legal innovations engineered in the aftermath of Covid-19 also face several challenges. To begin with, as a multi-annual spending programme stretching beyond the pandemic, NGEU will need to be properly managed by the EU institutions and successfully implemented by the member states. Moreover, NGEU has been technically designed as temporary instruments, specifically designed to address an exceptional occurrence like Covid-19. It remains to be seen however if the mechanisms can be discontinued, particularly as the EU faces the socio-economic fallout of the return of war in the European continent. In fact, EU responses to Russia's invasion of Ukraine seem to track the common debt instrument employed during the pandemic, which suggest that the NGEU template can sediment into the EU legal order and be turned into more permanent feature thereof (Fabbrini 2023). Finally, while the approval of the fiscal responses to the pandemic did not require any change to the EU Treaties, and could safely be accomplished on the basis of the existing legal framework, there is little doubt that the advances in fiscal integration occurred since the explosion of Covid-19 have also exposed several structural shortcomings in the EU system of governance. In particular, the limited involvement of the EP on decisions about borrowing, spending and taxes poses a democratic conundrum, which must be addressed at the earliest via appropriate constitutional reforms.

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